

World Safety Journal

A peer-reviewed journal,
published by the World Safety Organization

Journal Homepage:
<https://worldsafety.org/wso-world-safety-journal/>

Behavioral Economics of Safety Culture Management in Companies

Harbans Lal*

A Retired Professor of Psychology, SNTD Women's University, India

KEYWORDS

Behavior
Safety
Culture
BBS
Management
Companies
Economics
India

ABSTRACT

Most businesses are more concerned with making money and increasing profits than with ensuring the safety of their workers. Why do business leaders and employers refuse to invest in safety culture, as though they are unconcerned or unresponsive to risky work practices that result in disasters, incidents, family pain, and long-term consequences? They are probably unaware that the benefits of implementing safety in any company, large or small, far outweigh the financial benefits of not doing so.

1. INTRODUCTION

Profits should not be made at the expense of the health and safety of employees. Paul O'Neill saw that safety is an opportunity to boost profit and productivity while lowering medical and compensation costs and improving the bottom line (Berthold, 2016). Reduced lost employee hours, hospital costs, sick leave, pollution costs, property damages, and insurance premiums are all benefits of a safe work environment, all of which lead to higher productivity (Ekenedo, 2013).

Over the years, it has been debated whether willful violations of systems rules and procedures can be explained by system designers and managers failing to follow some behavioral economics propositions: firstly, unclear rules; secondly, delayed or ambiguous feedback; and thirdly, conflicts between high and low-level safety commitments (Battmann and Klumb, 1993).

Organizational safety culture management is heavily influenced by behavioral economics. The theoretical underpinning of safety culture is that it represents how people think and behave in connection to safety; it is a proactive method for enhancing occupational safety by focusing on the company's safety systems and its people's safe behaviors. The term "safety culture" has several definitions (Vu & De Cieri, 2014). Employee perceptions, attitudes toward organizational safety goals, everyday safe behavior, and the company's safety mechanisms to support safe behavior are all represented in the existing safety culture, according to the American Petroleum Institute (2015). (Cooper, 2018).

According to the Journal of Accounting and Economics, U.S. company executives, under market pressure to fulfill profitability expectations, may put workers' health and safety at risk in order to please investors (Smith, 2017). More than forty standards dealing with occupational safety and health have been adopted by the ILO, providing tools for governments, businesses, and workers to set procedures

* *Corresponding Author*: kailahl@hotmail.com

that ensure optimal workplace safety. However, the reality for millions of workers is quite different (ILO, 2021). Behavioral economics can help us discover solutions to regulate or ethically influence organizational biases and cognitive limitations, in order to help create company value (Deloitte, 2021). According to the ILO (2021b), health and safety management is an essential part of running a company to ensure that dangers and risks cannot harm employees.

This study examined the role of behavioral economics in safety management in order to create more lucrative judgments by analyzing potential concerns with at-risk behavior perception.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The economic benefits of health and safety management are enormous, with a return of 2.2 Euros for every Euro invested in OSH (Tanya, 2021). According to recent studies, it is behavioral economics 'money' that provides the solution, as well as actionable insights for employers and governments as they bargain between safety management and profits (Jaggi, 2021). Behavioral science insights can help firms better understand how they make financial decisions related to health, safety, and the environment (HSE). As a result, behavioral economics is critical to a company's long-term safety culture implementation (Dash, 2020).

Behavioral economics refers to the economic decision-making processes of individuals and institutions (Academy 4SC, 2021). Safety culture is about the values, beliefs, norms, practices, competencies and behaviors of an organization in relation to HSE. (Drummond and Pietikainen, 2021). International studies on the return on investment in prevention show that every unit invested in safety and health generates a potential benefit of more than two units of positive economic effects. The improvement of safety and health protection in the company does not necessarily mean an increase in expenditure (DGUV, 2021).

The Covid-19 situation underlines the importance of the balance between economy and health, taking into account the interactions between safety and microeconomics, in order to support this type of decision-making in the sense of a cost-benefit analysis and profitability analysis in safety culture management (Chao et al., 2021). The Covid-19 pandemic has shown how important occupational safety and health protection are for protecting the health of employees, for the smooth functioning of our societies, and for economic and social action. The European Commission renews its commitment to update health and safety at work by adopting the EU Strategic Framework for Health and Safety at Work 2021-2027; it set out the measures needed to improve the health and safety of workers over the next few years (European Commission, 2021).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research has shown that the behavioral economics of safety culture management is a relevant, critical and important concern for companies. With that in mind, it was a good idea to examine various findings from field workers, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic when economic security issues were a real concern. Both primary data (interviews, discussions) and secondary data (incident and accident rates) were collected. Interviews based on open-ended questions and personal in-depth discussions with 309 HSE, medical, educational, management and psychiatric professionals were conducted over a time period of two months (from June to July 2021) using remote data collection techniques from various locations and organizations in India. The non-random convenience, as well as snowball sampling techniques, were used to collect the relevant data. The participants were selected from the researcher's contact list and invited via WhatsApp and email to take part in the online survey.

4. DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

A key element of this research was data collection, which was carried out by means of controlled interviews and questionnaire surveys. A total of 500 people participated in this study, 309 of whom completed a field-of-action survey with the researcher. These research participants had introduced a behavioral safety culture in their workplaces. The research participants involved CEOs, directors, managers, department heads and security professionals from public and private industrial sectors, including chemicals, construction, gas, energy and steel.

Roughly 84% of the study participants said that they did not support a zero-harm policy. Almost 90% of the study participants felt that the main reasons why Indian companies are unwilling to spend on safety are: ignorance, cost, wrong regulation, abuse of regulation, and the reluctance of workers. The study participants noted that behavior and safety are positively correlated, and that when doing root-cause analysis, the underlying cause of safety implementation is people's behavior. The study participants (about 78%) also noted that increased involvement in safety awareness reflects a good safety culture.

The greatest challenge in the implementation of the behavioral safety culture program is the involvement of all employees, including contract employees, which is only possible when the fear of making punctual corrections to endangered behavior at the workplace has been removed from the minds. In other words, the approval of every employee is paramount to a successful implementation. This can be demonstrated by department heads and other senior leadership teams through visible actions that strengthen safe behavior and reduce risk behavior (Cooper, 2020). Employees should be encouraged to report any risky behavior openly and without fear, using the 'no-fault, no mistake, no name's method with the main objective of correcting behavior on the ground in order to reduce the risk of accidents or incidents, as suggested by 86% of the study participants.

The principle of positive safety culture management ensures that companies generate sustainable profits. Eight-eight percent of the study participants believed that a strong safety culture ensured that everyone is empowered, responsible for safety, and pursues safety on a daily basis by making punctual corrections of unsafe behavior without fear, with the primary goal of Zero Harm for everyone. The study participants feel that when an employee is valued, heard and really cared for, his or her attitude towards the company becomes different in a positive way. This, consequently, forces management to create an environment in which employees feel comfortable when they encounter safety risks or risky behavior (Michie, 2020).

The study participants (89%) also noted that organizations that do implement a behavioral safety approach ensure that no one is being harmed. However, they noted that establishing a safety culture is not only associated with a change in behavior, but also with a change in the mindset. The economics of implementing a behavioral safety culture in companies was noted by 82% of the study participants who indicated that unsafe practice leads to disaster and that every disaster, like road accidents, railway accidents, fire accidents, etc., is beyond an economic evaluation;

Generally speaking, the study participants felt that Indian companies do not appear to be aware that spending on safety is an investment and not an expense!

5. CONCLUSIONS

During the past 15 months, the world has witnessed the direct and indirect effects of a pandemic that took the lives of millions of people around the world and left millions at risk with its devastating and

painful effects. Due to the lack of awareness among urban and suburban communities, the spread of the pandemic had been uncontrollable! This could have been avoided, or the extent of the harm reduced if people had behaved responsibly by following various Covid-19 appropriate behaviors to limit the deadly effects (Nature Human Behavior, 2020).

By all means, a strong safety culture begins with the visible commitment of management and highly committed and capable employees at all levels. This would lead to satisfied stakeholders through reduced costs, increased reliability, reduced maintenance and better product quality, as well as benefits through motivated employees and satisfied customers; this could have direct consequences on business sustainability and profitability.

Eighty-one percent of the study participants stated that the behavioral safety culture was an instrument with which risks from occupational health and safety, as well as process safety, can be successfully limited. This behavioral science approach is currently being used successfully in numerous companies around the world (Geller, 2001).

There is a need to expand the behavioral safety culture program to include employee families and other key stakeholders in society, especially children and adolescents. This could only be achieved through the intervention of educational institutions and public forums that raise awareness of a behavioral safety culture in order to make it a way of life! Occupational health and safety management (OSH) can and should be viewed in monetary terms as part of a business system (Eastern Kentucky University, 2021). Annual safety reviews are critical to continued development; these are often not actively addressed by managers. What is important is that changing the hierarchy of safety controls at the sites is very important; this is also not so strongly emphasized by HODs. Most importantly, every employee plays 5 minutes of safety time every day, which is set as the SOP, an important role in developing a good safety culture. Performance reviews must be used as part of the safety culture to maintain a safe work environment (Hestbak, 2019).

The development of an interdependent safety culture is on the agenda for future-oriented companies in order to ensure long-term sustainability. The best way to identify company culture is by how its employees behave outside of the workplace. A common vision of the people of a zero-harm future would be the foundation of a safety culture that is reflected in safety beliefs, values, attitudes and daily behavior. It is important to motivate and motivate employees to pursue the behaviors that contribute to a strong HSE culture (Scace, 2018).

6. SCOPE OF FUTURE RESEARCH

It is important to remember that poor occupational health and safety costs money. Good occupational safety is good for business (EU-OSHA, 2021). The industry longs for social well-being. Safety is the core value in the industries of developed nations. The benchmarking of the safety statistics of all industrial nations has changed dramatically. Environmental standards are also implemented as disciplinary benchmarks. Due to the spread of the Covid-19 pandemic, occupational safety standards have been drastically improved. But, safety goes far beyond that! It still starves for benchmarking excellence. The number one cause of any injury caused by an incident is behavior. This also has a cascading effect on environmental health (Chao et al., 2021). Understanding changes in working conditions and deciding on company practices for safety, health and wellbeing would be critical (Glorian et al., 2021). Anticipate, prepare and invest now in resilient occupational safety and health systems (ILO, 2021a). Understanding the biggest risks in the workplace is the first step to better protecting employees and the bottom line (Liberty Mutual Insurance, 2021).

REFERENCES

- Academy 4SC (2021). Introduction to Behavioural Economics: Acting Irrationally. Retrieved on 26 July 2021 from <https://academy4sc.org/video/introduction-to-behaviours-al-economics-acting-irrationally/>
- Alcumus eCompliance (2021). 8 Steps to Building a Successful Behavior Based Safety Program. Retrieved on 12 August 2021 from <https://www.ecompliance.com/blog/behavior-based-safety-success/>
- American Petroleum Institute (2015). Pipeline safety management systems standard (ANSI/API RP 1173).
- Battmann, Wolfgang & Klumb, Petra. (1993). Behavioural economics and compliance with safety regulations. *Safety Science*. 16. 35-46. 10.1016/0925-7535(93)90005-X.
- Berthold, Janice (2016, Nov 04). Profits Should Not Come at the Cost of Workplace Safety. Retrieved on 15 August 2021 from <https://www.industryweek.com/operations/safety/article/21992214/profits-should-not-come-at-the-cost-of-workplace-safety>
- Cooper, D. (2020). Faces of EHS: Talks Behavioral Safety and Managing COVID-19. Retrieved on 14 August 2021 from <https://ehsdailyadvisor.blr.com/2020/03/faces-of-ehs-dominic-cooper-talks-behavioral-psychology-and-managing-covid-19/>
- Cooper, M.D. (2018). The Safety Culture Construct: Theory and Practice. In: Gilbert C., Journé B., Laroche H., Bieder C. (eds) *Safety Cultures, Safety Models*. Springer Briefs in Applied Sciences and Technology. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-95129-4_5
- Dash, Sanket Sunand (2020, December 20). Behavioural Economics: A New Driver of Strategic HRM. *NHRD Network Journal*, Volume: 14 issue: 2, 206-215. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2631454120977240>
- Deloitte (2021). Behavioural economics and management. Retrieved on 29 July 2021 from <https://www2.deloitte.com/us/en/insights/focus/behaviours-al-economics.html>
- DGUV (2021). About Vision Zero. Retrieved on 29 July 2021 from <https://www.vz-rsi.in/about>
- Drummond, James, and Pietikainen Anna (2021). How behavioural science can promote safety culture. Retrieved on 27 July 2021 from <https://apolitical.co/solution-articles/en/how-behavioural-science-can-promote-safety-culture>.
- Eastern Kentucky University (2021). The Economic Aspect of Health and Safety. Retrieved on 30 July 2021 from <https://safetymanagement.eku.edu/blog/the-economic-aspect-of-health-and-safety/>
- Ekenedo, Golda (2013). Framework for developing and sustaining safety culture in a developing economy. *European Journal of Applied Sciences*. 1. 28 -37.
- European Commission (2021). Occupational safety and health in a changing world of work. Retrieved on 11 August 2021 from https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_21_3170
- EU-OSHA (2021). Good OSH is good for business. Retrieved on 15 August 2021 from <https://osha.europa.eu/en/themes/good-osh-is-good-for-business>
- Geller E. Scott (2001). Behavior-based safety in industry: Realizing the large-scale potential of psychology to promote human welfare. *Applied & Preventive Psychology* 10:87-105 (2001). DOI: 10.1017.S0962184902010028
- Glorian Sorensen, Jack T. Dennerlein, Susan E. Peters, Erika L. Sabbath, Erin L. Kelly, & Gregory R. Wagner (2021). The future of research on work, safety, health and wellbeing: A guiding conceptual framework, *Social Science & Medicine*, Volume 269.

- Jaggi, Gautam (2021, Mar 23). How behavioural economics can enable a safe return to work. Retrieved on 28 July 2021 from https://www.ey.com/en_in/megatrends/how-behavioural-economics-can-enable-a-safe-return-to-work
- Johnson, Sara (2021, July, 26). Global economic growth depends increasingly on Covid19 vaccination progress. Retrieved on 29 July 2021 from <https://ihsmarkit.com/research-analysis/global-economic-growth-depends-Covid19-vaccine.html>
- Hestbak, Brad (2019 September 11). How can performance reviews be used as part of safety culture and maintaining a safe work environment? Retrieved on 30 July 2021 from <https://www.safeopedia.com/how-can-performance-reviews-be-used-as-part-of-safety-culture-and-maintaining-a-safe-work-environment/7/8088>
- ILO (2021). International Labour Standards on Occupational Safety and Health. Retrieved on 28 July 2021 from <https://www.ilo.org/global/standards/subjects-covered-by-international-labour-standards/occupational-safety-and-health/lang--en/index.htm>
- ILO (2021a). World Day for Safety and Health at Work 2021. Retrieved on 11 August 2021 from <https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/safety-and-health-at-work/events-training/events-meetings/safeday2021/lang--en/index.htm>
- ILO (2021b). How can occupational safety and health be managed? Retrieved on 14 August 2021 from <https://www.ilo.org/global/topics/labour-administration-inspection/resources-library/publications/guide-for-labour-inspectors/how-can-osh-be-managed/lang--en/index.htm>
- Liberty Mutual Insurance (2021, July 21). 2021 Liberty Mutual Insurance Workplace Safety Index Helps Companies Better Protect Employees and Control Costs as the Economy Continues to Reopen. Retrieved on 15 August 2021 from <https://www.libertymutualgroup.com/about-lm/news/articles/2021-liberty-mutual-insurance-workplace-safety-index-helps-companies-better-protect-employees-and-control-costs-economy-continues-reopen>
- Michie, S. (2020). Behavioural strategies for reducing covid-19 transmission in the general population. Retrieved on 14 August 2021 from <https://blogs.bmj.com/bmj/2020/03/03/behavioural-strategies-for-reducing-covid-19-transmission-in-the-general-population/>
- OSHA (2021). Business Case for Safety and Health. Retrieved on 14 August 2021 from <https://www.osha.gov/businesscase>
- Scace, Emily (2018, Sep 17). Safety Culture 2018: Seven Life Lessons from E. Scott Geller. Retrieved on 31 July 2021 from <https://ehsdailyadvisor.blr.com/2018/09/safety-culture-2018-seven-life-lessons-from-e-scott-geller/>
- Smith, Sandy (2017, May, 16). Are Injuries Still the ‘Cost of Doing Business’ at Some Companies? <https://www.ehstoday.com/safety/article/21919024/are-injuries-still-the-cost-of-doing-business-at-some-companies>
- Tanya (2021). Economic benefits of health and safety management. Retrieved on 11 August 2021 from <https://www.econonline.com/blog/economic-benefits-health-safety-management>
- Vu, T., & De Cieri, H. (2014). Safety culture and safety climate definitions suitable for a regulator: A systematic literature review (Research report 0414-060-R2C). Monash University.